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Abstract

This study examines the influence of a brand image variable on purchase intention toward t-shirt theme merchandise's purchase intention among the followers of the Instagram account @barasuara within Indonesia's indie music industry ecosystem. The research implemented a quantitative explanatory approach with a purposive sampling technique to analyze how audience's perceptions of band identity and their digital communication able to shape consumer purchasing behavior, these data were collected through an online questionnaire with a total of 230 Barasuara Instagram followers as respondents and further analysis using descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, and simple linear regression. The findings show that respondents tend to have a highly positive perceptions toward Barasuara's artistic identity, particularly in terms of musical quality, creativity, emotional value, and artistic uniqueness. Study also reveals that Barasuara brand image has a positive and significant influence on purchase intention toward Barasuara merchandise. The regression analysis revealed that brand image contributed 23.1% to respondents' purchase intention behavior, indicating a moderate relationship between the two variables. Beyond commercial considerations, the findings suggest that merchandise consumption within indie music communities may also reflect emotional attachment, symbolic participation, and audience identity. The Study also reveals that social media platforms such as Instagram play a role as a resilience medium in maintaining the sustainability of the Indonesian indie music industry through audience engagement and their support for merchandise produced by the digital music community. This study contributes to the discussion of digital marketing communication, consumer behavior, and sustainability within Indonesia's digital creative industry ecosystem.

Keywords: Brand Image, Purchase Intention, Indie Music, Instagram, Music Merchandise, Digital Creative Industry

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Music is one form of symbolic communication that transmits emotions, ideas, and social experiences through musical elements such as melody, rhythm, harmony, and song lyrics (Pring et al., 2024). Over generations, music has evolved beyond its role as an entertainment and artistic expression to become a big part of the creative industry with both economic and cultural value inside. In today's industry, music is produced, promoted, and consumed as the one of the cultural products that is supported by various marketing strategies and digital distribution systems (Guo, 2023; Pushmin, 2023).

The growth of digital technology has significantly reformed the way music is distributed, shifting from physical media to digital platforms and social media, so that allow the musicians to independently publish their work of art, reach wider audiences, and build direct interactions with fans through internet-based platforms (Eiriz & Leite, 2017; Geurts & Cepa, 2023). This transformation formed as a new ecosystem within the modern music industry that involves musicians, social media, fan communities, and digital creative economy activities, therefore change the distribution patterns, and accelerating the circulation of musical genres and cultural influences across different communities (Guo, 2023). Audiences can now easily access music from various cultural backgrounds and interact directly with artists through social media platforms, and encouraged musicians to become more adaptive in maintaining audience engagement while strengthening their artistic identity in increasingly competitive digital spaces.

The development has also created a bigger opportunity for independent musicians, commonly known as indie musicians, which be able to grow without relying entirely on major record labels, that characterized by the use of digital platforms and social media. Therefore independent artists enable to distribute their music more independently while building direct relationships with audiences (Frenneaux, 2023). In Indonesia, the indie music scene has continued to expand through music

communities, independent performances, and the use of digital platforms for music distribution and promotion (Resmadi, 2024). The example of Indonesia indie bands such as Efek Rumah Kaca, White Shoes & The Couples Company, The Adams, and Banda Neira has already contributed to the growth of Indonesia's independent music culture through their distinctive musical identities and independent production approaches through the music communities, live performances, and alternative distribution channels that support musicians outside mainstream record label systems (Hermawan & Abiyusuf, 2022). And in this context, Barasuara is also one of the well-known indie bands in Indonesia, namely an alternative rock band that has been active since 2012 and has been recognized for its distinctive musical character and strong artistic identity. Furthermore, in recent years Barasuara has also gained recognition through various achievements in the Indonesian music industry, involving awards and collaborations that further strengthened their position within the national indie music scene (Hartati, 2024; Sembiring, 2025).

Apart from their music promotion, indie musicians also rely on social media to shape their brand image and promote merchandise to their audiences within functions not only as a commercial product but also as a representation of community identity and a monetization strategy within the digital creative industry. Through platforms such as Instagram, musicians can strengthen engagement with fans, reinforce their brand image, and increase consumers' purchase intention toward the products they offer (Ali & Naushad, 2023; Ao et al., 2023). Merchandise such as band t-shirts, posters, and album-themed products often become symbolic representations of emotional attachment between musicians and fans (M. Lee et al., 2025). For many audiences, purchasing merchandise is not merely a transactional activity but also a form of participation and identity expression within a particular music community (Ngo et al., 2024).

Previous studies have shown that brand image and social media activities influence consumers' purchase intention (Ali & Naushad, 2023; Simbolon et al., 2022; Waworuntu et al., 2022). But the research specifically seeks to fill the research gap between the impact brand image on indie band on the purchase intention of song related merchandise remains limited, because only a few studies have explored the relationship between brand image, music merchandise, and social media from the perspective of resilience in the digital creative industry ecosystem. While this study specifically, examines the interrelationship between brand image, music merchandise and social media in the context of Indonesia's indie music industry.

In the increasingly challenging and uncertain digital creative industry environment, indie musicians are no longer rely primarily on music distribution as their primary source of income, instead, these musicians build a sort of digital ecosystems around themselves which involving social media, fan communities, and merchandise as strategies to sustain their creative businesses. So that the indie musicians expected to be able to maintain audience loyalty through digital engagement as an important factor in supporting the sustainability and resilience of the creative industry ecosystem. Merchandise sales, audience interaction, and community participation can contribute to alternative income sources while simultaneously strengthening the long-term relationship between musicians and listeners.

Therefore, this study aims to analyze the influence of Barasuara's brand image on consumers' purchase intention toward song-themed merchandise among Instagram followers of @barasuara as part of understanding the resilience of the digital creative industry ecosystem. Against this background, this study examines how Barasuara's brand image influences consumers' purchase intention toward song-themed merchandise among followers of @barasuara on Instagram. By exploring the relationship between brand image, social media, and music merchandise within the digital creative industry, this study contributes to the discussion of digital marketing communication and consumer behavior. In

In addition, the findings may provide insights for independent musicians in utilizing social media and merchandise strategies to strengthen audience engagement and support the sustainability of creative business ecosystems.

Literature Review

Computer-Mediated Communication (CMC)

Computer-Mediated Communication (CMC) describes communication that takes place through digital technologies and internet-based platforms, allowing individuals and groups to interact without being physically present in the same place or time (Kaye et al., 2022). The development of social media today has expanded these forms of interaction by enabling users to exchange information, maintain relationships, and engage with audiences in virtual environments. And in the music industry, Computer-Mediated Communication helps to understand how musicians use social media such as Instagram to communicate with audiences, build artistic identities, maintain fan engagement, and promote their creative works.

Computer mediated communication is also related to the interactive characteristics of digital communication, because audiences are not only passive recipients of information but are also able to respond, participate, and engage directly with content shared by musicians, through social media features such as comments, likes, reposts, and direct messages able to create opportunities for two-way communication between artists and audiences (Kaye et al., 2022), that may strengthen emotional connections, encourage audience participation, and support the formation of online fan communities that contribute to the sustainability of musicians' digital presence.

Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB)

The Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) by Icek Ajzen explained how behavioral intention is shaped by attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control (Ajzen, 1991). In the consumer

behavior studies, TPB has frequently implemented to understand how consumers' perceptions and evaluations of a product influence their intention to purchase it, therefore TPB is highly relevant in examining purchase intention in contemporary digital marketing and online consumer environments (Lavuri, 2022).

For this research study, Barasuara brand image is one of a factor that may encourage a positive attitudes from audiences toward the band's song-themed merchandise, this is because the favorable brand image may increase audiences' interest in purchasing merchandise associated with Barasuara's musical identity. And In this context, Theory of Planned Behavior provides a theoretical perspective to understanding the relationship between brand image and purchase intention within the context of the indie music industry and digital communication.

Brand Image

Brand image reflects the perceptions and associations that consumers may form toward certain brand through information, experiences, and communication activities related to that brand, therefore a good brand image can strengthen consumer trust, foster emotional attachment, and increase purchase intention (Çavuşoğlu et al., 2021; Zollo et al., 2020). Within the indie music industry, brand image is created not only by musical works themselves, but also by social media presence and visual identity, and of course the directly interaction, that communicated by musicians across digital platforms (Cheung et al., 2020; Matusin et al., 2023; Odoom, 2025).

The perceptions of consumers of certain brand image are influenced not only by product quality, but also by visual representation, reputation, communication style, and emotional associations attached to the brand, that may be developed through a repeated communication activities and audience experiences across digital platforms (J. K. Lee, 2021). In the contexts of digital marketing, the content of social media and audience interactions contribute significantly to how consumers interpret brand

identity and credibility, therefore a strong brand image may increase audience recognition, strengthen emotional attachment, and encourage consumers to consider products associated with the brand in future purchasing decisions.

From the perspective of independent music industry, brand image is often connected to authenticity and artistic consistency, because the audiences tend to value musicians who are perceived as having originality, emotional sincerity, and a distinctive creative identity. These perceptions influence how audiences emotionally connect with musicians and also how they evaluate products associated with the artists, therefore, the image that formed through music and digital communication may become an important factor influencing audience loyalty and purchasing behavior within indie music communities.

Purchase Intention

In the digital marketing perspective, purchase intention can be used to predict future consumer purchasing behavior, that may be influenced by factors such as brand image, promotional activities, emotional attachment, and audience engagement through social media platforms. And this is become the reason why then purchase intention related to the tendency of the consumers to buy certain product arises after consumer evaluating information and forming perceptions about the product or brand (Ali & Naushad, 2023).

In digital environment, purchase intention may also appear through consumers' curiosity and interest in seeking additional information about products before making purchasing decisions, because the audiences frequently could explore product reviews, designs, pricing information, and social media content before developing purchase consideration (Petcharat & Leelasantitham, 2021). This is the exploratory behavior, that reflects how digital communication and social media exposure can gradually

shape consumers' purchasing tendencies toward products associated with musicians, brands, and online communities.

Indie Music Groups

Indie music groups are form of artists that independently produce, distribute, and promote their art without relying on major record labels, and often emphasize artistic freedom, authenticity, and closer relationships with their audiences (Aryandari & Hendrawan, 2025; Cheung et al., 2020). Therefore the expansions of digital platforms and social media allow indie musicians to sustain creative business activities by build fan communities and expand the reach through digital engagement and merchandise strategies (Odoom, 2025).

The growth of indie music communities has also contributed to the sustainability of independent music ecosystems, because they often rely on community networks, independent performances, and digital platforms to distribute and promote their work to wider audiences (Hermawan & Abiyusuf, 2022). The communities provide opportunities for collaboration, audience development, and the circulation of musical works outside mainstream industry systems, as the benefit of digital technology expand to an advance level, indie musicians increasingly utilize social media and online distribution channels to maintain creative independence while strengthening communication with their audiences.

Compared to mainstream artists who can rely on large-scale promotional systems, indie musicians commonly build audience engagement through community interaction, storytelling, and consistent artistic representation, thus making them more likely to tend to develop stronger emotional relationships with audiences because communication often occurs more directly and personally through digital platforms (Hermawan & Abiyusuf, 2022). This closeness may strengthen fan loyalty and

encourage audiences to support musicians not only through music consumption but also through merchandise purchases and participation in fan communities.

Conceptual Framework

This research explores the relationship between the brand image and the purchase intention in the Indonesia's indie music industry, and in this context, Barasuara's brand image will reflect how audiences perceive the band's artistic identity, credibility, and emotional appeal through their music, visual representation, and Instagram presence.

As an independent group, Barasuara is recognized for its creativity independence and authenticity in producing and promoting music without relying heavily on major record labels, so this allows Barasuara to maintain a distinctive artistic identity and build closer communication with its audience through digital platforms. In the independent music ecosystem, audiences often value originality, emotional sincerity, and direct interaction between musicians and fans, and based on these characteristics the emotional connection between audiences and the band may strengthen and contribute to a more positive perception of Barasuara's image. Consequently, the indie identity carried by Barasuara becomes an important foundation in shaping audience trust, loyalty, and interest toward products associated with the band.

The merchandise that are taken as an object in this research consists of song-themed apparel inspired by Barasuara's musical works and artistic concepts, that also represent fan identity and emotional attachment to the Barasuara itself. For many audiences, merchandise serves as a symbolic representation of their connection to the music, values, and community associated with the band, and through merchandise purchases, fans may express personal identity, demonstrate support for musicians, and participate in indie music culture as part of a broader creative community.

While social media precisely Instagram plays an important role in how Barasuara communicates with its audience, shares creative content, and maintains its artistic image, thereby the interactions and representations presented through social media may shape audience perceptions and influence their intention to purchase merchandise related to the band.

The relationship can also be associated through the Theory of Planned Behavior, which explains that positive attitudes toward an object may encourage a behavioral intention toward that object, and in this study, a positive perception of Barasuara's brand image is able to strengthen audiences' intention to purchase the band's song-themed merchandise.

Research Method

Research Approach and Design

This study applies a quantitative approach and implements an explanatory research design to verify the relationship between brand image variable and purchase intention variable within the Indonesia's indie music industry context. Quantitative research allows researchers to measure the relationships between variables through statistical analysis based on a numerical data that collected from respondents (Creswell & Creswell, 2018; Hartanto et al., 2022). Afterwards, the research design functions in this research are to analyze and determine whether Barasuara's brand image are able to influences the audiences' purchase intention toward song theme t-shirts merchandise. Furthermore, this research specifically focuses on the relationship between brand image as the independent variable and purchase intention as the dependent variable among followers of the Instagram account @barasuara.

Population and Sample

The population in this study consists the Instagram followers of @barasuara account as the main official account of Barasuara itself. Instagram followers is selected as they are directly exposed to the

Barasara's communication activities on social media, including music promotion, visual content, audience interaction, and merchandise-related posts. Furthermore, during the data collection period, the account approximately has 247,000 followers. The method to determine the sample size on this research is based on recommendations for quantitative survey research proposed by Hair et al. (Memon et al., 2020), which recommend a sample size of five to ten respondents for each measurement indicator. As the study used 23 indicators, the recommended sample are ranged from 115 to 230 respondents.

This study uses purposive sampling as a non-probability sampling technique that selects respondents based on criteria relevant to the objectives of the study (Tajik et al., 2024). Respondents were required to:

- Know Barasara as an indie music group;
- Follow the Instagram account @barasara;
- Have seen Barasara's content on Instagram; and
- Be familiar with merchandise related to Barasara's songs or musical identity.

Data Collection Technique

The data was obtained through an online questionnaire that distributed to a selected-respondents. The online questionnaires were chosen as a medium as they allow efficient data collection among digitally active audiences and Instagram users (Likert, 1932). Furthermore, the questionnaire is designed to be measure the audience perceptions regarding Barasara's brand image and their purchase intention toward song-themed merchandise t-shirt with a five-point Likert scale ranging from strongly disagree (1) to strongly agree (5). On this research, the secondary data are also collected from academic journals, books, and previous studies related to brand image, digital communication, social

media marketing, indie music, and purchase intention apart from questionnaires collection as the primary data.

Research Variables

Variable were used in this research are divided into independent dan dependent variable. Brand Image as independent variable, is referring to the audiences' perceptions of Barasuara's identity, credibility, reputation, and overall image as an indie music group. On this case, independent variable was measured through indicators that related to the value, personality, reputation and music quality from audience perception. In addition, the Dependent Variable is Purchase Intention, which referring to the respondents' tendency to purchase the Barasuara's song-themed merchandise. This variable was measured through an indicators that related to the interest, willingness to seek information, product preference, and intention to purchase merchandise products.

Instrument Development and Operationalization of Variables

Research instrument was chosen based on operationalization of variables derived from previous theoretical frameworks referring to the brand image and purchase intention (Kotler & Keller, 2021). On this instrument, questionnaire consisted of structured statements is designed to measure respondents' perceptions toward Barasuara's image as an indie music group and audience tendency to purchase song-themed merchandise products.

The brand image variable is divided into a several dimensions, the dimensions are adapted to fit the context of the music industry and social media communication. The dimensions consist of corporate image, user image, and product image. On the, corporate image dimension is to reflects audiences' perceptions regarding Barasuara's *identity, consistency, reputation and credibility* as an independent music group (Kotler & Keller, 2021). The dimension is considered as important due to the reputation and credibility frequently influence audience trust and emotional attachment toward musicians and

entertainment brands. From the perspective of independent music culture, audiences often associate music groups not only by musical products but also with emotional values, personal identity, and social meaning represented by the artists (Berné et al., 2025). Therefore, user image dimension focuses on how audiences perceive the persona that represented by Barasuara through their music, communication style, and daily interaction on social media. Lastly, product image dimension was used to measure the perceptions from audiences to the quality, accessibility, and overall value of Barasuara's musical products and merchandise. Indicators in this dimension included the respondents' perceptions to music quality, artistic arrangement, emotional relevance, and listening experience associated with Barasuara's releases. As the merchandise products are closely related to the band's musical identity, respondents' evaluation of the music itself is considered relevant in shaping purchase intention.

The dependent variable, purchase intention is measured using the indicators that related to preferential interest and exploratory interest. Preferential interest refer to the respondents' tendency for prioritizing Barasuara merchandise over alternative music merchandise products. This dimension able to describe respondents' product preference, loyalty, and willingness to repeatedly purchase merchandise associated with the band. Before deciding to purchase, audiences usually search for additional information regarding product designs, prices, or availability. This behavior shows exploratory purchase intention among the followers of Barasuara. The dimension includes indicators such as information-seeking behavior, curiosity toward product design and pricing, and willingness to explore available merchandise collections. Therefore, from digital marketing contexts the exploratory behavior is important as the social media audiences often to engage in information seek activities before developing purchase intentions. Furthermore, all of the variable above were measured using a five-point Likert scale ranging from strongly disagree (1) to strongly agree (5). The existence of the Likert scale allows respondents to express their level of agreement toward each statement systematically and

enables researchers to quantify audience perceptions for statistical analysis (Likert, 1932). Likert scales are commonly used in the marketing and communication research as they provide flexibility in measuring attitudes, perceptions, and behavioral tendencies among respondents.

Respondent Characteristics

All of the respondent were the followers of the Instagram account @barasuara that reach the purposive sampling standard established by the researcher. Respondents were also selected based on their familiarity with Barasuara's music and social media activities apart from the basic demographic information such as gender and age. Focusing on Instagram followers is relevant due to Instagram functions as the primary communication platforms used by Barasuara to interact with audiences, distribute band related content, and promote merchandise. Through social media application, audiences are exposed not only to promotional information but also to visual branding, artistic storytelling, and emotional communication that may contribute to the formation of brand image.

Social media audiences tend to develop a parasocial relationships with musicians and public figures through repeated exposure to online content (Ravi & Patki, 2025). These interactions may influence emotional attachment, consumer perceptions, and purchasing tendencies toward products associated with artists or music groups. The followers of @barasuara were considered appropriate respondents for examining the relationship between brand image and purchase intention in the context of indie music merchandise.

Validity and Reliability Testing

To ensure the quality of the research instrument, validity and reliability tests were conducted before proceeding to the main data analysis stage. Validity testing is implemented to determine whether each questionnaire item was accurately capable to measure the intended research variable. Furthermore, reliability testing is conducted to evaluate the consistency and stability of respondents'

answers across questionnaire items. The validity and reliability testing are important as the valid instrument indicates that the statements included in the questionnaire are relevant to the theoretical concepts that being measured while reliability test in quantitative research appears to demonstrates whether an instrument can produce consistent measurements if applied to respondents with similar characteristics.

On this research, reliability testing was conducted using Cronbach's Alpha coefficient (Francis et al., 2025; García-García et al., 2025). This approach generally considered variable as reliable when the Cronbach's Alpha value exceeds the acceptable threshold commonly used in social science research. Furthermore, the implementation of validity and reliability testing is important as the findings depend heavily on the quality of the measurement instrument. By ensuring that all questionnaire items meet validity and reliability requirements, the researcher can improve the credibility and accuracy of the statistical analysis results.

Classical Assumption Testing

Classical assumption tests were carried out to conduct the simple linear regression analysis, and to ensure that the collected data met the statistical assumptions required in regression analysis (Alita et al., 2021). These tests are important as violations of statistical assumptions may affect the accuracy and interpretation of regression results (Shatz, 2023). Through these statistical procedures, this test aims to ensure that the regression model is appropriate and statistically reliable. Which could lead enabling an accurate interpretation of the influence of Barasuara's brand image on audiences' purchase intention toward song-themed merchandise (Jones et al., 2025).

Data Analysis Technique

Data analysis from the collected data were analyze using a descriptive statistics and simple linear regression analysis. The descriptive statistics were used to recap respondents' perceptions of

brand image and purchase intention, while simple linear regression analysis was applied to examine the influence of brand image on purchase intention (Ghanad, 2023). Although before running the regression analysis, validity and reliability tests were conducted to make sure the research instrument was both accurate and consistent. Classical assumption tests were also applied to check whether the data met the required conditions for regression analysis (Toyoda, 2024). Ultimately, these procedures were used in this study to examine how Barasuara's brand image influences audiences' purchase intention toward song-themed merchandise within the context of digital music marketing and social media communication.

Results

Brand Image

To examine the examine respondents' perceptions of Barasuara as an independent music group, a descriptive analysis was conduct. The analysis uses standard deviation and mean score based on 230 respondent's response. The result describes the generally respondents had highly positive perceptions of Barasuara's identity, creativity, musical quality, and emotional value. In summary, the Brand Image variable recorded a mean score of 4.59 with a standard deviation of 0.43, indicating a very high level of agreement among respondents.

Table 1.

Brand Image Descriptive Statistics

Item	Mean	SD	Category
X1	4.59	0.582	Very High
X2	4.61	0.547	Very High
X3	4.62	0.577	Very High

Item	Mean	SD	Category
X4	4.58	0.613	Very High
X5	4.64	0.565	Very High
X6	4.58	0.591	Very High
X7	4.57	0.622	Very High
X8	4.45	0.733	High
X9	4.58	0.613	Very High
X10	4.69	0.582	Very High

Value and creativity indicate that Barasuara is seen as representing certain ideals and values that align with listeners' personal preferences and identities. In addition, findings also describe that Barasuara's brand image was shaped not only through commercial efforts, but also through the symbolic and emotional meanings. The highest mean score was found in item X10 (M = 4.69), which describe respondents highly appreciated the complexity and uniqueness of Barasuara's musical arrangements. On the other hand, the lowest score appeared in item X8 (M = 4.45) that suggesting the accessibility and ease of enjoying Barasuara's music in different situations were perceived slightly lower compared to other indicators. This relatively lower score implies to while respondents generally enjoy Barasuara's music, some may see their style as more niche to certain moods rather than casual listening. As an alternative rock band with complex arrangements and poetic lyrics, Barasuara seems appeal more to listeners who engage with music as an emotional or artistic experience rather than as background entertainment. In summary, the consistently high mean scores across all brand image indicators describe respondents not only recognize Barasuara as a musically skilled group. But also perceive them

having a distinctive and strong artistic identity compared to other Indonesian independent musicians.

They commonly associated with creativity, emotional depth, and authenticity, which can be seen in their musical style, lyrical themes, and visual presence on social media.

The findings also describe audiences assess Barasuara beyond just technical musical quality, several indicators show that respondents view the band as consistent, and professionals in their artistic approach. This perception may also be influenced by their communication on Instagram, which; visual aesthetics, performance content, and storytelling elements help shape how audiences understand the band's identity. Overall, the findings conclude that respondents perceive Barasuara as a music group with a strong artistic identity, consistent musical direction and emotional authenticity. At the same time, the results also indicate that perceptions of the band's image are generally very positive.

The low standard deviation values suggest that respondents' views are relatively similar, indicate a similar understanding of Barasuara's artistic credibility and identity consistency. In digital music environments, this consistency becomes especially important as audiences are constantly exposed to various content and competing entertainment options. A strong and recognizable image therefore plays a key role to maintaining audience attachment and supporting fan engagement. The strong agreement among respondents about emotional embedded in their music and communication style.

Purchase Intention

The descriptive analysis of Purchase Intention describes respondents generally expressed a positive interest to purchasing Barasuara merchandise. The variable recorded an overall mean score of 3.96 with a standard deviation of 1.09, indicating a relatively strong level of purchase intention among respondents.

Table 2.

Purchase Intention Descriptive Statistics

Item	Mean	SD	Category
Y1	3.76	1.087	High
Y2	3.70	1.086	High
Y3	3.97	1.127	High
Y4	3.51	1.263	Moderate
Y5	3.80	1.162	High
Y6	3.86	1.168	High
Y7	4.17	1.023	High
Y8	4.31	0.885	Very High
Y9	4.18	1.007	High
Y10	4.11	1.030	High
Y11	4.15	1.112	High
Y12	4.21	1.107	Very High
Y13	3.76	1.215	High

Descriptive findings on Purchase Intention indicate respondents generally show favorable attitudes toward merchandise associated with Barasuara. Beyond functional purchasing motives, respondents also view merchandise as a symbolic expression of their emotional connection to the band and its musical identity. The highest mean score was found in Item Y8 (M = 4.31) indicating strong interest in seeking information of merchandise through social media platforms, this shows that social media platforms play an important role in encouraging information-seeking behavior among audiences.

Item Y12 also recorded a high mean score ($M = 4.21$), describing a strong intention among respondents to purchase Barasuara merchandise. Similarly, the high mean score on Item Y12 indicates that respondents show a relatively strong behavioral intention to purchase Barasuara merchandise products.

The findings suggest that positive perceptions of the band gradually influence audiences' willingness to financially support the artist through merchandise consumption. Respondents demonstrated strong interest in exploring merchandise-related information through Instagram and other digital platforms before making purchase decisions. For independent musicians, merchandise often serves not only as a commercial product, but also as an extension of artistic identity and a form of fan engagement. This finding reflects digital communication environments may enable audiences to participate not only as music listeners, but also as active consumers who engage with; promotional content, product visuals, and community discussions.

The lowest mean score was found in Item Y4 ($M = 3.51$) indicating respondents did not always prioritize Barasuara merchandise over alternative products. This score suggests although audiences hold positive attitudes toward the band, their purchasing decisions may still be influenced by other factors such as; price, personal preferences, purchasing power, and the relevance of the product to everyday use. In other case, the relatively higher standard deviation values in the Purchase Intention variable indicate greater variation in respondents' behavioral tendencies compared to their perceptions of Brand Image. Which describe although respondents generally share similar positive views of Barasuara's image, their actual purchase intentions appear to be more diverse. This is understandable, as purchase intention is often influenced by various situational and personal factors beyond emotional attachment alone.

In summary, the descriptive analysis shows that respondents have a relatively strong purchase intention toward Barasuara merchandise. Specifically in terms of information-seeking behavior and

future purchase consideration. In other words, the finding also suggests that Instagram communication activities along with the positive brand image developed by Barasuara may contribute to shaping audience interest in merchandise products. These results reinforce the idea that independent musicians can strengthen audience engagement not only through their music, but also through; consistent digital presence, visual communication, and meaningful interactions with followers. In this context, merchandise functions as part of a broader symbolic relationship between artists and audiences within digital music culture.

Validity and Reliability Test

The results indicate that all indicators exceeded the minimum threshold value of 0.30 after conducting a validity test using corrected item-total correlation analysis. Score above 0.30 indicating that all questionnaire items are valid and appropriate for measuring the research variables.

Table 3.

Validity Test Results

Variable	Range of Correlation	Interpretation
Brand Image	0.531 – 0.699	Valid
Purchase Intention	0.665 – 0.877	Valid

The Brand Image variable recorded corrected item-total correlation values ranging from 0.531 to 0.699, while the Purchase Intention variable ranged from 0.665 to 0.877. In summary, all indicate items were adequately represent and statistically valid to represent the constructs used in this study.

Reliability testing was conducted using Cronbach's Alpha coefficient, this approach may determine a variable as reliable when the coefficient exceeds 0.70.

Table 4.

Reliability Test Results

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	Interpretation
Brand Image	0.899	Highly Reliable
Purchase Intention	0.966	Highly Reliable

Table results show that both variables have a positive internal consistency. The Brand Image variable acquire a Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.899, while Purchase Intention obtained a value of 0.966. These results indicate that all questionnaire items are suitable and reliable for further statistical analysis.

Normality Test

Kolmogorov–Smirnov and Shapiro–Wilk tests were used as the medium of test to conduct normality testing, the results showed significance values below 0.05. Which indicating that the data were not perfectly normally distributed, however this study involved 230 respondents and considered a relatively large sample size. In a social science research, a minor deviation from normality is common in Likert-scale surveys because respondent tend to cluster in higher agreement categories. In addition, refer to normal Q-Q plot and histogram describe the data distribution as generally followed the expected pattern without major irregularities. The skewness values for both variable Brand Image (-1.249) and Purchase Intention (-0.997) may indicate a moderate negative skew toward higher response categories. Furthermore, the data were considered acceptable for parametric statistical analysis.

Correlation Analysis

Pearson Product Moment to test the correlation analysis was conducted to examine the relationship between Brand Image variable and Purchase Intention variable. This test revealed a correlation coefficient value of 0.481 with a significance value below 0.001, which indicating a positive

and statistically significant relationship between Brand Image and Purchase Intention. A stronger-perceptions regarding Barasuara’s brand image were shown from the positive correlation that associated with a higher intention to purchase Barasuara’ merchandise. Furthermore, the coefficient value indicates a moderate relationship between the two variables.

Regression Analysis

To determine the influence of Brand Image on Purchase Intention toward Barasuara merchandise, a simple linear regression analysis was conducted. This finding shows the regression model obtained an R value score of 0.481 which indicate a moderate positive relationship between the variables. The coefficient of determination (R^2) reaches a score of 0.231, indicating that Brand Image describe 23.1% of the variance in Purchase Intention, while the remaining 76.9% may also have been influenced by other external factors. While The Durbin–Watson value of 1.846 shows that the regression model did not experience serious autocorrelation problems. Furthermore, The ANOVA test also demonstrated the regression model was statistically significant ($F = 68.465$; $p < 0.001$) which indicating that the model is appropriate for explaining the relationship between two variables.

Table 5.

Regression Coefficient Results

Variable	B	Beta	Sig.
Brand Image	1.328	0.481	<0.001

The regression equation is presented:

$$Y = -9.478 + 1.328X$$

This regression coefficient indicates that every single one-unit increase in Brand Image is predicted to increase Purchase Intention by 1.328 units. These findings shows that a positive perception

about Barasuara's artistic identity, creativity, professionalism, and emotional value significantly contributed to respondents' tendency in purchase merchandise associated with the band.

Discussion

Finding of this study reveal brand image has a positive impact and significant influence on purchase intention toward Barasuara merchandise among Instagram followers. The regression analysis explains the brand image significantly contributed to respondents' purchase intention indicating that a stronger audience perception regarding Barasuara's artistic identity, musical credibility, and emotional value tended to increase their desire to purchase t-shirt song-themed merchandise. From the perspective of the independent music industry, brand image appears to function as a commercial identity and a symbolic representation of; artistic authenticity, emotional engagement, and audience attachment. These findings able to support previous studies that suggesting brand image plays an important part in influencing consumer behavior and purchase intention within the digital marketing environments (Ali & Naushad, 2023; Zollo et al., 2020). This study emphasizes the role of; artistic authenticity, emotional attachment, and symbolic consumption within Indonesia's indie music communities. The findings also suggest audiences may perceive music merchandise both as commercial products and a representation of identity and emotional affiliation with musicians (Mohammed & Balqis, 2025). As the previous studies primarily focus on commercial branding and conventional digital marketing products.

The descriptive analysis revealed respondents are generally possessed highly positive perceptions toward Barasuara's artistic identity. Indicators that related to the musical quality, emotional value, creativity, and artistic uniqueness obtained particularly high scores. The strongest indicators were found in respondents' perception about Barasuara's musical arrangements were complex but still enjoyable to listen to. These finding suggest musical sophistication and artistic originality contribute

significantly to the formation of a strong brand image among indie music audiences. From the perspective of independent music culture, artistic authenticity may also function as an important symbolic value that distinguish independent musicians from mainstream commercial artists (Frenneaux, 2023; Negus & Astor, 2022). Previous studies suggested that indie music audiences often value the originality, artistic consistency, and emotional sincerity as an important aspect to audience engagement and identity formation (Cheung et al., 2020; Odoom, 2025). Accordingly, Barasuara's artistic image may also strengthen emotional resonance between the band and their audiences, which later on influences consumer intention toward the merchandise associated with the band's identity.

As the previous studies primarily focus on commercial branding and conventional digital marketing products, this study also emphasizes the role of; artistic authenticity, emotional attachment, and symbolic consumption within Indonesia's indie music communities. The findings also suggest that audiences may perceive music merchandise as commercial products and also as a representation of identity and emotional affiliation with musicians (Mohammed & Balqis, 2025).

The findings can also be explained through the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) that proposed by Ajzen (1991). This theory explains that a positive attitudes toward an object may encourage a behavioral intention toward that object. In this scope, respondents who perceived Barasuara in a positive way as a creative and emotionally engaging music group demonstrated a stronger intention to purchase merchandise related to the band. The finding demonstrates that a favorable audience evaluation toward artistic identity and brand representation may also contribute to the consumer behavioral intention within digital music communities. The findings also highlight the important role of digital communication platforms within the independent music ecosystem. Indicators that related to searching for merchandise information through social media obtained some of the highest scores within the purchase intention variable.

Although the function of Theory Planned Behavior (TPB) on this research was used as a conceptual framework to explain the form of behavioral intention which including the purchase intention dimension based on the framework. Nevertheless, this research is not intended to examine the whole construct of the theory of planned behavior such as perceived behavioral control & subjective norms. This research focus is directed to the influence of brand image towards the merchandise purchase intention of t-shirt song themed merchandise. So that the research model is simplified to the direct relation between brand image and purchase intention variable and were analyze using the simple linear regression method. Therefore, theory of planned behavior functionates as theoretical framework that supports the understanding of purchase intentions. While the empirical testing of this research focused on the role of brand image as one of factors that able to influence purchase intention.

This research finding is also relevant to the concept of Computer-Mediated Communication (CMC), which explains how digital technologies facilitate interaction and relationship-building within online environments (Kaye et al., 2022). Through social media app such as Instagram, musicians are able to communicate artistic messages, maintain audience relationships, and strengthen emotional attachment through visual content, music promotion, and merchandise-related communication. Therefore, digital communication may also contribute to strengthening the audience engagement and supporting consumer purchase intention within online music communities. This finding able to reflects how social media platforms such as Instagram function not only as promotional channels but also as spaces for interaction, audience engagement, and brand communication (Kaye et al., 2022; Odoom, 2025; Onofrei et al., 2022).

More than that, the findings strengthen argument about the digital communication environments have fundamentally transformed the relationship between musicians and audiences within the contemporary creative industries. Instagram application enables audiences to experience

continuous exposure to Barasuara's artistic narratives, visual identity, and symbolic representation through interactive digital content. Unlike a traditional one-way promotional communication, social media platforms facilitate reciprocal interaction between musicians and audiences through; comments, reposts, story engagement, and direct communication features. These interactions have tendency to strengthen the emotional attachment and form a sense of perceived closeness between audiences and musicians, which later on contributes to stronger brand perceptions and consumer behavioral intention.

The findings are consistent with the previous studies which emphasizing the importance of social media in shaping brand image and consumer behavior. Ali and Naushad (2023) stated digital marketing communication through social media significantly contributes to forming positive brand perceptions and influence on purchase intention. Similarly, Simbolon et al. (2022) reveal on Instagram-based promotional activities may strengthen audience awareness and influence consumer decision-making processes. The present study increases these findings by demonstrating within indie music environments, social media communication functions beyond commercial promotion alone. Instagram becomes part of the artistic ecosystem which musicians communicate authenticity, emotional narratives, and symbolic meanings associated with their music and merchandise.

In addition to support this findings, Lee et al. (2025) argue that merchandise products may function as a symbolic object representing the affiliation of emotion and fan identity within the fanbase. On the independent music communities, audiences frequently adapt merchandise not only because of utilitarian value, but also see merchandise as; shared cultural values, emotional attachment, and participation within a particular music community (Cheung et al., 2020; Odoom, 2025). This dimension may explain how respondents demonstrated relatively strong information-seeking behavior regarding merchandise despite showing moderate preference exclusivity toward Barasuara products compared to alternative merchandise brands. Although, correlation analysis further explains a moderate positive

relationship between brand image and purchase intention. Apart from the relationship was statistically significant, the coefficient of determination showed that brand image explained only 23.1% of the variance in purchase intention.

The relatively moderate regression coefficient suggests that emotional admiration towards a musician does not always translate directly into purchasing behavior. This finding predicts that while brand image is an important factor, consumer purchasing behavior toward music merchandise also can be influenced by other factors such as lifestyle preferences, fan loyalty, product quality, pricing, and fashion trends, and broader consumer culture factors. This can be seen through the lowest indicators within the purchase intention variable were respondents' tendency to prioritize Barasuara merchandise over alternative products. This finding indicates the audiences may possess emotional attachment toward the band without necessarily prioritizing its merchandise as their primary consumption choice. Consumers may also continue to compare music merchandise with products from other bands or lifestyle brands before making any purchasing decisions. This will reflect that the competitive nature of the digital creative industry, where symbolic consumption is influenced by broader lifestyle and consumer culture factors.

Moreover, the findings suggest that indie musicians increasingly operate not only as music producers but also as a cultural brand that rely on; audience engagement, symbolic communication, and digital identity management. As stated in the Geurts and Cepa (2023) study about digital transformation in the music industry, technological developments have expanded the role of music beyond entertainment products into broader identity-oriented branding systems. Within this context, merchandise becomes a part of a larger creative economy strategy that supports musicians' financial sustainability, strengthens fan communities, and maintains long-term audience relationships. From a wider perspective, these findings highlight the development of relationship between music branding,

audience engagement, and sustainability within the digital creative industry ecosystem. Independent musicians are increasingly relying not only on a music streaming revenue but also take a big part on merchandise sales, digital branding, and social media engagement as strategies to sustain creative business activities. Within the independent music communities, merchandise may also function beyond utilitarian purposes by representing identity expression, emotional support, symbolic participation, and community affiliation.

This study contributes theoretically by integrating the perspectives of brand image, Computer-Mediated Communication (CMC), Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), and independent music culture into the discussion of consumer behavior within digital creative ecosystems. Findings also suggest independent musicians should not focus primarily on promotional intensity, but also prioritize artistic consistency, emotional storytelling, audience interaction, and symbolic representation through their digital platforms. These elements appear to play an important part to strengthening emotional engagement and encouraging consumer intention toward music-related merchandise products while supporting the sustainability of creative business ecosystems.

Despite all of the findings, this study has several limitations as the research focused only on Instagram followers of Barasudara and examined brand image as a single predictor of purchase intention. Future studies may also explore an additional variable such as fan loyalty, parasocial interaction, lifestyle identity, perceived product quality, or community engagement to obtain a more comprehensive understanding of consumer behavior within digital music ecosystems.

Conclusion

This study analyzes the influence of Barasudara's brand image on audiences' purchase intention toward song-themed merchandise within the Indonesia's independent music industry. The findings indicate that brand image positively and significantly affects and take parts in purchase intention.

Suggesting to the audiences who perceive Barasuara as creative, emotionally meaningful, and artistically band are more likely to show interest in purchasing merchandise associated with the band. The study also highlights the important role of social media specifically Instagram that increasingly shaping communication and audience engagement within contemporary music communities. Respondents demonstrated a strong interest in seeking information that merchandise related through social media, indicating digital platforms have become more than promotional spaces. For independent musicians, social media platforms such as Instagram allow interaction with audiences through visual storytelling, artistic representation, and everyday communication that help maintain emotional connection and audience involvement.

Merchandise also appears to carry meanings that extend beyond commercial consumption in the context of independent music culture. For many audiences, merchandise also functions as a symbolic expression of identity, emotional attachment, and a participation within a music community. This suggests that the relationship between musicians and audiences is not only formed through musical products, but also through shared cultural values and emotional experiences that communicated across digital environments. Furthermore, the findings suggest artist authenticity and consistency of digital representation remain important to build audience trust and attachment. Barasuara's strong artistic identity, musical originality, and emotional presentation may also have contributed to how audiences perceived the band and its merchandise positively. In this part, digital branding within the indie music communities is closely connected to; authenticity, emotional resonance, and the ability of musicians to sustain meaningful interaction with their audiences over time.

Theoretically that this study contributes to discussions surrounding brand image, digital communication, and consumer behavior by demonstrating how symbolic and emotional dimensions of music culture may also influence the purchase intention within online communities. This study also

supports the relevance of Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) and Computer-Mediated Communication (CMC) to understanding the audience behavior within the contemporary digital music environments. In addition, the findings also suggest that independent musicians benefit from maintaining artistic consistency, strengthening audience interaction, and utilizing social media not only for promotional medium but also for sustaining a long-term relationship with their audiences. Merchandise strategies may become effectively when they are integrated with emotional storytelling, artistic identity, and community-oriented communication.

Nevertheless, this study focused specifically on an Instagram follower of Baraswara and examined the brand image as the primary predictor of purchase intention. Future studies may also explore other additional factors such as; fan loyalty, parasocial interaction, lifestyle identity, perceived product quality, or community participation to provide and explain a broader understanding of audience behavior within indie music ecosystems. Comparative studies involving different music genres, musicians, or digital platforms may also offer an insight into how digital communication influences merchandise consumption and audience engagement in contemporary creative industries.

Author Contributions: Conceptualization, Marginata K. Putra and Rizky P. Hidayat; methodology, Marginata K. Putra and Rizky P. Hidayat; software, Rizky P. Hidayat; validation, Lahandi Baskoro; formal analysis, Marginata K. Putra and Rizky P. Hidayat; data collection, Rizky P. Hidayat; writing, Marginata K. Putra and Rizky P. Hidayat. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available in Zenodo at

10.5281/zenodo.21029064

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